

SEPSIS

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Abstract : Sepsis is a common infectious disease caused by the spread of purulent microbes from the local source of infection to the bloodstream, lymphatic system, and from them to all tissues and organs of the patient.

Infected wounds and purulent diseases in various areas (eg, scabies, abscesses, and phlegmon) can be a source of sepsis. Germs such as staphylococci, streptococci, and sometimes pneumococci, gonococci, and Escherichia coli also cause sepsis. In fact, sepsis is a complication of an injury or inflammatory process in the body. Serious illnesses, surgeries, excessive blood loss, sudden weight loss, vitamin deficiencies, and malnutrition all play a role in its development.

The harder it is, the more damage

When sepsis is severe, the germs in the blood multiply very quickly and they contaminate the blood with their own toxins, such as red blood cells (erythrocytes). When sepsis develops, the patient's body temperature rises to 39-40 degrees, the flesh becomes swollen, and sometimes sweats profusely. Occasionally there is a rash on the skin, which can turn yellow.

When sepsis is mild, the germs do not multiply in the blood, but spread through the bloodstream to various organs and tissues, resulting in a large number of pus-filled lesions. In this case, the sepsis lasts longer, and the patient's condition worsens during the accumulation of pus, and somewhat relieves it after the rupture (or after surgery). In both cases of sepsis, the patient has a fever, headache, profuse sweating, low blood pressure, weakness, loss of appetite, and often insomnia. In addition, enlargement, swelling of the liver and spleen, deterioration of heart and kidney function are observed. The patient develops small black spots on the limbs and inflammation of the joints and muscles. In young children, sepsis is usually in the form of pneumonia.

External and internal factors play an important role in the development of sepsis. For example, it sometimes occurs after being bitten by insects (mosquitoes, gnats, mites, fleas, spiders). It also sometimes occurs when there is infection in open wounds on the skin, delayed wound healing, various gangrenes (mainly leg gangrene), after surgery on the abdominal organs, and as a complication of acute surgical diseases.

There are many types

Gynecological sepsis occurs after certain changes or diseases of the genitals (for example, an abortion performed in an uncomfortable environment, a difficult birth, purulent endometritis, salpingitis).

Cryptogenic sepsis is often caused by autoinfections under certain conditions, i.e. infections can be located in the tonsils, dental granulomas, dilated bronchi, intestines, spleen.

Tonsillogenic sepsis is often caused by pus-filled tonsils and necrotic inflammation (angina).

Rhino genic sepsis is a complication of purulent disease of the nose and adjacent cavities.

Urosepsis is caused by an infection of the genitourinary system, damage to it, and purulent processes in these organs.

Surgical sepsis is a complication of various surgical conditions (especially purulent peritonitis, pleurisy, appendicitis, lung abscess, and burn injury).

In addition, sepsis can occur in newborns.

Infant sepsis (neonatal sepsis) is a common infectious disease in which bacteria enter the bloodstream from an infectious site. Infection can occur in the antenatal (prenatal), intranasal (during labor) and postnatal (postpartum) periods. Sepsis develops very quickly, especially in premature babies.

To prevent sepsis, consider the following:

open wound pus;

facial whitening;

chip output;

appearance of rash (acute purulent inflammation of the tissues of the fingers);

phlegmon (acute purulent inflammation of the subcutaneous fat);

prolonged healing of minor skin lesions;

burning somewhere in the body.

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